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Decarbonization Pathways for Indonesia's Power Sector: An OSeMOSYS Scenario Analysis

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study employs the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) to analyze alternative decarbonization pathways for Indonesia's power sector to 2050, in line with the National Electricity Plan (RUKN 2025-2060) and the government's Net Zero Emission 2060 target. Three scenarios are examined: a Business as Usual (BAU) pathway reflecting historical trends, a policy driven RE 60% scenario incorporating carbon capture and storage (CCS) and nuclear power, and a Net Zero Emission RE 100% scenario excluding coal and CCS. The analysis considers electricity demand growth, generation mix, installed capacity, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and system costs, with the objective of identifying trade offs between affordability, sustainability, and reliability.

The results reveal marked differences among the scenarios. The BAU pathway remains highly dependent on fossil fuels, resulting in emissions of 503 MtCO₂ by 2050, with renewables constituting only 20.4% of installed capacity. The RE 60% scenario achieves substantial emissions reductions to 21 MtCO₂ in 2050 through CCS retrofits and nuclear deployment. However, it incurs the highest discounted system cost (USD 1,468 billion), largely due to the capital intensity associated with CCS technologies. By contrast, the RE 100% scenario entails the most extensive system expansion (209.47 GW by 2050) but achieves net zero emissions by 2050 while delivering the lowest total discounted cost (USD 1,240 billion), even lower than BAU, owing to early renewable deployment and fuel cost savings.

The findings carry significant policy implications, showing that partial decarbonization strategies reliant on CCS are economically less attractive than full decarbonization, as they incur the highest system costs while delivering only moderate reductions in fossil fuel dependence. In contrast, the RE 100% pathway demonstrates that a full transition to renewables and nuclear can achieve net zero emissions at 2050 while minimizing long term system costs. These results suggest that prioritizing early and decisive investments in renewable energy and nuclear capacity provides both environmental and economic advantages, positioning Indonesia on a more cost effective trajectory toward its NZE 2060 target.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia's power sector is undergoing a critical transition as the country pursues ambitious climate and energy targets. The Enhanced Nationally Determined Contribution commits to a 31.89% unconditional reduction in GHG emissions by 2030, rising to 43.20% with international support, while the Long Term Strategy for Low Carbon and Climate Resilience sets the aspiration of Net Zero Emissions (NZE) by 2060 or earlier (Government of Indonesia, 2022). Achieving these targets requires structural changes in the power system, including the gradual retirement of coal fired power plants, accelerated deployment of variable renewable energy (VRE), and the integration of storage and carbon capture technologies.

The National Electricity Plan (RUKN) provides the official framework for electricity development, projecting long term demand growth, generation mix, and capacity additions. However, evaluating the feasibility of decarbonization pathways requires not only analyzing the RUKN aligned scenario, but also comparing it with other plausible futures, such as a continuation of historical trends and a coal phase out trajectory (MEMR, 2025b).

Within this policy context, this study applies the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) to optimize alternative pathways for Indonesia's power sector. It is designed to support cost effective and sustainable energy transitions by enhancing transparency, stakeholder engagement, and public acceptance in decision making (Hersaputri *et al.*, 2024). The analysis covers electricity demand, generation mix, installed capacity, GHG emissions, and system costs up to 2050. By contrasting a Business as Usual (BAU) pathway based on historical growth, a policy driven target (RE 60%) and Net Zero Emission (RE 100%), the study provides insights into the trade offs between affordability, sustainability, and energy security in Indonesia's transition to a low carbon future.

The primary objective of this study is to explore and compare decarbonization pathways for Indonesia's power sector using OSeMOSYS. The specific aims are to:

1. Develop a BAU baseline by projecting historical demand and capacity trends without new policy intervention.
2. Model the policy driven target (RE 60%) to reflect Indonesia's official policy pathway for electricity planning extended to 2050.
3. Explore the Net Zero Emission (RE 100%), excluding coal and coal with CCS, to assess the implications of accelerated fossil retirement.
4. Compare the scenarios in terms of installed capacity, generation mix, GHG emissions, and system cost.
5. Provide insights for policymakers and stakeholders on the strategic options for achieving Indonesia's NZE 2060 commitment while balancing cost, reliability, and sustainability.

This study is guided by the following research questions:

1. How will Indonesia's power sector evolve under a BAU pathway compared to policy driven (RE 60%) and Net Zero Emission (RE 100%)?
2. Which pathway delivers the most cost effective and low emission outcomes by 2050?
3. What are the trade offs between system cost, emissions reduction, and technology choices across different scenarios?

METHODOLOGY

This study employs the OSeMOSYS, an open source energy system modelling framework widely applied in energy transition and planning studies (Plazas-Niño *et al.*, 2025). OSeMOSYS determines the least cost technology mix to satisfy electricity demand while adhering to defined technical and policy constraints, such as emission caps, capacity expansion limits, and renewable energy targets. The modelling horizon is extended to 2050, with results analyzed in terms of generation mix, installed capacity, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and system cost.

The modelling is based on the Starter Data Kit for Indonesia, which provides a Reference Energy System, technology parameters, and cost assumptions derived from international and regional datasets. This baseline was refined and calibrated using national data sources, including:

1. Handbook of Energy and Economic Statistics of Indonesia (HEESI) 2022, 2023, and 2024, published by the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources (MEMR), for historical electricity demand, installed capacity, and fuel consumption (MEMR, 2023, 2024, 2025a).
2. National Electricity Plan (RUKN 2025-2060), which outlines projections for electricity demand, generation mix, and capacity expansion targets (MEMR, 2025b).

To explore Indonesia's power sector transition, three scenarios were developed using OSeMOSYS. The BAU scenario reflects historical demand and supply growth without new policy intervention. The RUKN aligned (Policy Scenario) follows the targets and assumptions of the National Electricity Plan (RUKN 2025-2060), extended to 2050. Finally, the Coal Phase Out scenario examines an accelerated transition by retiring coal earlier and replacing it with renewable energy and storage. These scenarios are summarized in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overview of the three scenarios used in this study

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

To meet the projected electricity demand of 2,513 PJ in 2050, two alternative transition scenarios were developed in addition to the BAU case. The RE 60% (Policy Scenario) emphasizes the deployment of Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) technology to replace conventional coal and natural gas power plants, complemented by the introduction of nuclear power starting in 2032. Nuclear power plants play an important role in Indonesia's electricity system as a reliable low carbon baseload option to complement intermittent renewables and support the Net Zero Emission target (Santosa *et al.*, 2023; Dwijatmiko *et al.*, 2024). This pathway reflects a balanced approach between maintaining dispatchable capacity and integrating renewable energy, with the target of reaching a 60% renewable share by 2050. Meanwhile, the RE 100% (Net Zero Emission Scenario) focuses on the acceleration of renewable energy expansion while ensuring grid stability. In this scenario, the energy mix by 2060 is designed to combine 40% Variable Renewable Energy (VRE) such as solar and wind, with 60% Stable Renewable Energy (SRE) including hydro, geothermal, biomass, and nuclear, to maintain system reliability and quality. Together, these scenarios provide contrasting yet complementary perspectives on how Indonesia can secure its growing electricity demand while advancing towards decarbonization targets.

Figure 2. Power Generation (2022 – 2050)

Figure 2 presents the projected electricity generation mix under three scenarios from 2025 to 2050. In the BAU pathway, coal remains dominant, rising from 832 PJ in 2025 to 1,742 PJ in 2050, with only limited growth of renewables. In contrast, the RE 60% scenario achieves a more balanced mix by 2050. Fossil fuels are partly retained through CCS, with coal CCS contributing 632.6 PJ and natural gas CCS 401.6 PJ. Renewables make up around 60% of total generation, led by hydro (313.9 PJ), nuclear (369.1 PJ), and wind (314.6 PJ).

The RE 100% scenario shows a complete shift away from fossil fuels by 2050. Coal generation falls to nearly zero, replaced by a substantial increase in clean technologies. Renewables and nuclear together supply 100% of demand, including wind (390 PJ), solar PV (153 PJ), nuclear (491.9 PJ), and hydro (840 PJ). Importantly, Variable Renewable Energy (VRE), solar and wind, accounts for about 21% of total generation in 2050, while the remaining share is provided by stable renewable sources (hydro, biomass, geothermal) and nuclear. Overall, while BAU results in continued fossil dependence, the RE 60% and RE 100% scenarios illustrate two distinct decarbonization pathways, CCS based stabilization versus full scale renewable and nuclear deployment, with the RE 100% pathway demonstrating the largest role for VRE integration.

Figure 3. Installed Capacity (2022 – 2050)

Figure 3 illustrates the projected total installed capacity across BAU, RE 60%, and RE 100% scenarios from 2025 to 2050, highlighting how decarbonization pathways affect system scale and technology composition. In 2050, the three scenarios show distinct differences in total installed capacity and technology shares. Under BAU, the system requires only about 103 GW, dominated by coal and natural gas, while renewables contribute a modest 20.4% of capacity. In the RE 60% scenario, capacity nearly doubles to 197 GW, reflecting a more diversified mix with coal CCS, natural gas CCS, nuclear, hydro, solar PV, and wind. Renewables together with nuclear reach 69.6% of the total, highlighting a significant transition away from fossil fuels.

By contrast, the RE 100% pathway requires the largest system expansion, reaching 209.47 GW, primarily driven by hydro and wind, complemented by solar, geothermal, biomass, and nuclear. In this case, renewables and nuclear provide the entire installed capacity, with VRE alone accounting for 37.7% of the total. Since high shares of VRE introduce intermittency challenges, energy system optimization models typically impose limits on the maximum share of VRE to safeguard reliability and reduce curtailment risks (Xu *et al.*, 2022). This demonstrates that higher reliance on renewables and nuclear not only eliminates fossil fuel dependence but also necessitates larger installed capacity to meet demand, due to the lower capacity factors of variable renewable technologies.

Figure 4. Annualized Investment Costs (2022 – 2050)

Figure 4 delineates the annualized investment costs across three scenarios from 2022 until 2050 in Billion USD. The analysis of annualized investment costs reveals that while the BAU pathway requires the lowest cumulative investment by 2050 (USD 175.6 billion), it is incompatible with Indonesia’s Net Zero Emission 2060 target and risks locking in fossil based infrastructure. The RE 60% scenario emerges as the most capital intensive option (USD 298.8 billion), largely because coal and natural gas plants are retrofitted with Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) technologies, which significantly increase capital costs, rising from USD 764 to 1,443 million/GW for natural gas and from USD 1,871 to 2,853 million/GW for coal. These higher unit costs explain the drastic escalation of capital expenditures in this pathway. Research consistently demonstrates that carbon capture and storage (CCS) significantly increases costs and reduces efficiency in coal and natural gas power plants (Shao *et al.*, 2024). By contrast, the RE 100% scenario requires lower cumulative investment (USD 200.2 billion), as early and decisive deployment of renewables reduces reliance on CCS retrofits, thereby lowering long term infrastructure costs and stranded asset risks. These findings suggest that partial decarbonization may paradoxically be more expensive than full decarbonization, and that front loading renewable investments offers not only environmental but also economic advantages in the long term.

Figure 5. Annual Fixed Operating Cost (2022 – 2050)

Figure 5 depicts the annual fixed operating costs for all scenarios from 2022 until 2050 in Billion USD. The comparison of annual fixed operating costs across scenarios shows relatively moderate differences between BAU, RE 60%, and RE 100%, with all three pathways converging around USD 60-70 billion by 2050. In the early years (2025-2030), the BAU scenario incurs slightly lower fixed costs compared to renewable oriented pathways, reflecting continued reliance on existing conventional infrastructure with relatively stable operating expenses. However, by 2040 and 2050, both RE 60% and RE 100% exhibit higher fixed costs, largely due to the larger installed capacity of renewables and supporting technologies that, despite lower variable costs, still require significant fixed expenditures for operation and maintenance. Importantly, the RE 60% pathway records almost the same fixed costs as RE 100%, despite higher overall capital expenditures, indicating that maintaining fossil assets with CCS does not provide a substantial advantage in terms of reducing fixed operating burdens. This suggests that while operating costs remain broadly comparable across scenarios, the choice of technology mix, particularly the reliance on CCS in RE 60%, drives up capital costs without generating meaningful savings in fixed operation and maintenance costs.

Figure 6. Annual Variable Operating Costs (2022 – 2050)

Figure 6 illustrates the annual variable operating costs for all scenarios from 2022 until 2050 in Billion USD. The results highlight a clear divergence in variable operating costs between fossil intensive and renewable oriented pathways. By 2050, the BAU scenario records the highest variable costs, approaching USD 182 billion, driven by continued dependence on coal and natural gas, where fuel expenditures and operational flexibility requirements escalate substantially over time. In contrast, both RE 60% and RE 100% scenarios maintain significantly lower variable costs, around USD 122-129 billion USD, reflecting the inherent cost advantage of renewables that rely on zero fuel resources. The similarity of outcomes between RE 60% and RE 100% indicates that once renewable penetration exceeds a certain threshold, variable costs become relatively stable, as fossil fuel dependence, and its associated volatility, declines sharply. This reinforces the conclusion that renewable energy expansion, regardless of pathway, reduces the economic exposure to fuel price risks and operational inefficiencies, while BAU remains highly vulnerable to escalating variable costs.

Figure 7. Total Discounted Cost (2022 – 2050)

Figure 7 presents the total discounted system costs across BAU, RE 60%, and RE 100% scenarios, highlighting the economic implications of different transition pathways. The BAU pathway requires approximately 1,265.9 billion USD, while the RE 60% scenario reaches 1,467.9 billion USD, and the RE 100% pathway decreases to 1,240.0 billion USD. When benchmarked against Indonesia’s GDP in 2024, which is reported at 1.43 trillion USD (International Monetary Fund (IMF), 2024), the implications are clear. The difference between BAU and RE 100% represents a reduction of 25.8 billion USD, equivalent to only 1.8% of Indonesia’s GDP in 2024, indicating that a full renewable transition is not only technically feasible but also economically modest relative to national income. Conversely, the additional cost of RE 60% compared to BAU amounts to 202.0 billion USD, equivalent to about 14.1% of GDP in 2024, highlighting that partial reliance on CCS technologies imposes a significantly higher economic burden. These findings suggest that pursuing a 100% renewable pathway could deliver long term cost savings, while the RE 60% pathway is less economically attractive despite its emission reduction potential.

Figure 8. Total Emission (2022 – 2050)

Figure 8 depicts the projected CO₂ emissions under the BAU, RE 60%, and RE 100% scenarios from 2022 to 2050. Under the BAU pathway, emissions increase steadily throughout the period, reaching 503.2 million tons CO₂ in 2050, driven by the continued reliance on coal and natural gas without significant mitigation measures. In contrast, the RE 60% scenario initially follows a similar trajectory but begins to decline markedly after 2035, reflecting the gradual integration of renewables, CCS, and nuclear power. By 2050, emissions under RE 60% are reduced to 21.04 million tons CO₂, representing a sharp departure from the fossil intensive BAU pathway. The RE 100% scenario achieves the most aggressive decarbonization, with emissions starting to decrease earlier, around 2025, and reaching net zero levels at 2050, owing to the accelerated penetration of renewables and phase out of fossil fuels. Overall, the figure highlights that BAU results in a continuous rise of emissions, whereas RE 60% and RE 100% both succeed in deep decarbonization, with the latter offering a faster and more complete pathway toward net zero.

While the results of this study provide important insights into the trade offs between BAU, RE 60%, and RE 100% scenarios, future work is needed to deepen the analysis and support policy design. Further research could incorporate more granular temporal and spatial resolution to capture variability in renewable resources, particularly under high shares of VRE. Sensitivity analysis on technology costs, fuel prices, and carbon pricing would strengthen the robustness of the results. In addition, integrating considerations of system reliability, and storage technologies will be critical to assess long term pathways toward achieving net zero with economic feasibility and operational security.

CONCLUSION

This study compared the BAU, RE 60%, and RE 100% scenarios to assess Indonesia's power system transition pathways toward 2050. The results highlight strong interconnections between generation mix, installed capacity, cost structures, and emissions. Under the BAU pathway, coal and natural gas remain dominant, leading to continuously rising emissions that reach 503.2 MtCO₂ in 2050. By contrast, the RE 60% scenario represents a transitional approach that combines CCS retrofits and nuclear deployment, achieving deep emission reductions to 21.0 MtCO₂, but at the expense of the highest total discounted cost (USD 1,467.9 billion) due to the capital intensity of CCS technologies. The RE 100% scenario, meanwhile, demonstrates the feasibility of a near-complete renewable transition, requiring the largest installed capacity (209.47 GW) but ultimately yielding the lowest total discounted cost (USD 1,240 billion) and net zero emissions at 2050, thus providing both environmental and economic advantages.

Installed capacity requirements follow an increasing order from BAU (102.9 GW), to RE 60% (197.2 GW), and RE 100% (209.47 GW), reflecting the lower capacity factors of variable renewables compared to fossil fuels. This drives higher investment needs in renewable oriented scenarios. Annualized investment costs are particularly pronounced in RE 60%, where coal and gas CCS retrofits raise capital requirements drastically compared to conventional plants. While fixed operating costs converge across all scenarios at around USD 60-70 billion by 2050, variable operating costs differ significantly, BAU escalates to nearly USD 181.74 billion, while both RE 60% and RE 100% stabilize around USD 122-129 billion, underscoring the long term cost advantage of fuel free renewables. Collectively, these findings confirm that partial decarbonization is paradoxically more expensive than full decarbonization, as it combines high capital expenditures with only moderate fossil fuel reductions, while full decarbonization achieves the most balanced outcome between climate ambition and cost efficiency.

Based on these results, several policy recommendations emerge. First, the government should establish a robust and transparent long term investment framework to accelerate renewable deployment while ensuring a gradual and managed phase out of coal. Second, targeted financial instruments, such as green bonds, blended finance, and public, private partnerships, are required to mobilize capital for high CAPEX technologies including solar, wind, hydro, and nuclear. Third, under the RE 60% pathway, research, development, and pilot projects on CCS should be prioritized to assess their technical feasibility and cost competitiveness, while under the RE 100% pathway, policy support should focus on large scale grid modernization and energy storage. To conclude, the implementation of coherent carbon pricing mechanisms and renewable portfolio standards will be critical to enhance the competitiveness of low carbon technologies. Aligning these measures with Indonesia's Net Zero Emission 2060 target will allow the trade offs identified in this study to be managed effectively, while safeguarding energy security, economic affordability, and environmental sustainability.

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Data Availability Statement: The data and model parameters employed in this study were prepared by Fernando Antonio Plazas Niño, serving as a trainer in the EMP APAC 2025 workshop organized by the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme. These datasets and modelling inputs were developed within the context of training activities and subsequently adapted for the Indonesian energy system case study presented in this paper. Access to the underlying data and model configuration can be obtained from the authors upon reasonable request.

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